

Indian Silk Industry Overview: Identifying Consumer Concerns

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Abstract:

Background: *The Indian silk industry has been booming worldwide, creating a mark for itself. India is home to some of the most exotic and wide-ranging silks globally. It occupies a distinctive position in the textile industry of India as it plays a significant role by contributing almost 15% of the world's total raw silk production and is also a dominant contributor to the textile exports from India. The silk industry also plays a significant role in elevating the rural economy of India. India happens to be the largest consumer of silk goods, mainly influenced by traditional clothing practices.*

Methods: *The present paper studies in depth the silk demographics of India. It keenly tracks the silk industry production, imports and exports and its future projections. In an attempt to understand the current consumer behaviour in relation to silk textiles, a survey has been conducted on 200 women aged between 20-60 years.*

Results and Discussion: *The results have been discussed to bring to light the critical consumer concern areas that the stakeholders in the silk industry need to focus on to strengthen their foothold further. The results of the survey highlight that many consumers do not use silk due to the expensive maintenance it requires such as drycleaning. Various other consumer patterns and concerns have come to light through the survey. The Indian silk industry is passing through a crucial phase of reorientation and adjustment necessitated by the market forces. The use of silk is becoming increasingly prevalent in the upcoming sectors such as home textiles and other technical textiles.*

Keywords: *consumer, export, import, India, silk*

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1. Introduction

Silk holds an unchallenged position as a mark of beauty and luxury, and is aptly known as the "Queen of Textiles". Its pleasing lustre, excellent drapability and comfort make it a sought-after fibre. To add to this are its properties of strength, flexibility, softness, and absorbency along with high wearer comfort. Silk is breathable and its isothermal properties make it cool in summers and warm in winters. Silk fibre's outstanding properties rival the most advanced synthetic polymers [1]. Thus, it can be said that silk is a remarkable material that has played a significant role in human history and continues to be valued for its many qualities today [2]. Silk has been known for its use in clothing for a long time, but more recently, it has become a contender for use in non-apparel products as well. This is partly because of its remarkable mechanical properties, as well as its ability to be both biocompatible and biodegradable.

Even though silk makes up a small percentage of the global textile market, i.e. less than 0.2%, its production base is spread over 60 countries in the world, the major producers being in Asia (95% of mulberry production and almost 100% of non-mulberry silk). The major silk-producing countries in the world are; China, India, Uzbekistan, Brazil, Japan,

Republic of Korea, Thailand, Vietnam, DPR Korea, Iran, etc. A few other countries are also engaged in the production of cocoons and raw silk in negligible quantities; Kenya, Botswana, Nigeria, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Bangladesh, Colombia, Egypt, Japan, Nepal, Bulgaria, Turkey, Uganda, Malaysia, Romania, Bolivia, etc. [5].

The European Union (EU) and the United States are the biggest consumers of silk outside the silk-producing countries of Asia. USA imports the largest quantities of silk textile and clothes. Japan is the country with the highest consumption of silk per capita. France, Germany, Italy, Switzerland and the United Kingdom are also leading silk consumers. Italy is the world's largest importer of waste silk which is spun into yarn for the production of knitwear [2].

1.1 Indian Silk Industry

The Indian silk industry has been successful worldwide in creating a mark for itself. It occupies a distinctive position in the textile industry of India as it plays a significant role by contributing almost 15% of the world's total raw silk production and also is a dominant contributor to the textile exports from India (Yaseen, 2013.) The added advantage is that sericulture is a labour-intensive, agriculture-based industry and thus, it plays a significant role in elevating the rural economy of India. Statistics reveal that India is the 2nd largest producer of raw silk in the world and produces raw

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silk to the tune of over 32,000 metric tonnes out of the global 1,75,000 metric tonne production (approximate values), next only to China which produces an enormous 80% share of the world production.

India also happens to be the largest consumer of silk goods, mainly influenced by the traditional clothing practices. This has also driven India to a position where the gap between the demand and supply of silk is filled by a large quantum of exports, majorly from China [3].

The current shift in the Indian population demographic structure, which leans towards professionally engaged women and a marked influence of the Western world on fashion choices, has resulted in a decrease in the use of silk clothing by Indians. The Indian silk industry is experiencing a critical phase of reorientation and adjustment necessitated by the market forces. The use of silk is becoming increasingly prevalent in the upcoming sectors such as home textiles and medical textiles (Technical textiles).

1.2 History

Silk has been produced in India from pre-Vedic times. India was strategically situated on the famous Silk Route, which stretched across Asia from China to the Mediterranean. Indian caravans laden with luxury goods like spices and indigo traded for silk from China. The Chinese have been known to keep the practice of sericulture a very closely guarded secret. It is popularly believed that a Buddhist monk smuggled the eggs of the silkworm into India, from where sericulture was established in India [4].

Fascinated by the elegance, princely rulers like Tipu Sultan of Mysore propagated and encouraged the cultivation of silk in India. Mughal emperors were also very fond of silk clothes and patronised the industry in Bengal and Kashmir. The British administration in India accorded top priority to silk cultivation in India, especially the Bengal region for the manufacture of parachutes. The first silk textile mill, on modern lines, was started by the East India Company at Haora in 1832. Later on, new factories also started in Karnataka (in 1845) and Kashmir (1892). The industry suffered a setback between 1875 and 1915 due to the occurrence of the perinea disease and the loss of the raw silk crop. However, it got boosted after tariff protection was granted in 1934. In the post-independent era, the Government of India identified the silk industry as an employment-oriented industry, suitable for the development of rural India. After independence, there has been a significant increase in the production of silk textiles in the country [4].

2. Methods and Materials

Extensive research was required to understand the Indian silk industry and its consumers to comprehend the silk industry's current situation. Phase one of the study involved conducting a thorough review of the industry's current status through accessible secondary sources. The second phase was to understand consumer behaviour towards the consumption of

silk textiles and their concerns with using silk. A thorough literature study was done in phase one. The data was tallied, sorted, and structured before being presented in the results and discussion section. To better understand consumer behaviour and patterns, a survey of 200 women aged between 20-60 years, residing in the Urban NCR region and belonging to middle and high-income groups was undertaken in phase two. A convenience sampling plan was employed and a google form was used for online data collection. The following section discusses the same study's findings.

3. Results and discussion

Silk is an integral part of Indian cultural clothing. Its use is not restricted to the fashion-conscious but is also deeply integrated into India's traditional clothing practices. Various parts of the country are centres of silk production, practising silkworm rearing, yarn production, fabric weaving and fabric finishing, including dyeing. Reports suggest that over sixty lakh people are directly involved in sericulture activities. The employment potential of this industry is immense, with a large section dedicated to rural employment. Statistical data reveals that sericulture generates substantial employment amounting to 11 man-days per kg of raw silk produced almost every year. Of the total revenue generated, 57 percent flows back to the cocoon growers in the rural areas; thus, a large share of income goes back to the villages from the cities. Hence, sericulture can also be seen as a tool for redevelopment reconstruction of rural areas.

3.1 Indian Silk Demographics

India is known for some of the most exquisite and wide-ranging varieties of silks in the world. It is the only country in the world to produce all five varieties of silk i.e. Mulberry, Tassar, Muga, and Eri. In fact, India holds a position of being the only country producing the non-mulberry, wild varieties of silk. The Indian silk market has a strong cultural holding and is to a large extent bound by traditions. Silk has been intermingled with the life and culture of the Indians. The below figure (Figure 1) depicts the relative production quantities of Mulberry, Tassar, Eri and Muga silks in India I between 2015-2021 (The figures for the past three years remain unavailable). From the Central silk board data for 2020-21. It is evident from the Central silk board data for 2020-21 that Mulberry silk makes up over 70% of the total silk produced in 2020-21. Of the remaining, 20% is Eri silk, 8% is tussar and a minimal quantity of muga silk. [4].

Figure 1: Domestic Raw Silk Production in India over Six Years

High fashion fabrics from classic dupion and taffeta silk to fine fabrics such as organza, crepe, georgette, chiffon have not only high domestic demand but also are sought after by international fashion designers across the globe. The Indian silk industry is very adaptable to the colours, weave patterns, prints, embroideries and appliqué work. It can be conveniently tailor-made to the designers' specifications, allowing the exporter to supply small quantities and endless varieties.

Silk production spans across the entire Indian subcontinent. Certain parts of the country undertake sericulture and also yarn and fabric production, whereas other centres are not involved in silk fibre production but are established centres for silk processing and weaving. Each silk producing centre is known for its uniqueness in patterns and designs. Traditional methods and modern techniques of production co-exist, resulting in a vast array of silk fabrics that find a unique place in the world. The varieties of fabrics produced by the silk handloom sector have a distinct character and individuality. There are various identified silk production centres. The map below (Figure 2) indicates the silk centres of India.

Figure 2 : Silk Centres in India

The above map indicates that mulberry silk is primarily produced in Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Jammu & Kashmir and West Bengal. The non-mulberry silks are produced in Jharkhand, Chattisgarh, Orissa and the north-eastern states. Karnataka contributes about 85% of the country's production by rearing multivoltine hybrids of a silkworm. This activity results in five to six crops a year. Due to their suitable climate, Jammu and Kashmir produce silk by

rearing univoltine silkworms. Other states, namely, Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh and Punjab, contribute roughly 1.8% to the total production of mulberry silk in India.

The tribes of Madhya Pradesh, Bihar, and Orissa traditionally rear tussar silkworms. These three states mainly contribute to the production of tussar silk in the country. The recent rearing of *Antherea royeri* & *Antherea pernyi* has enabled the country to produce the oak tussar silk in the sub-Himalayan belt and Manipur. Muga silk is grown exclusively in Assam, producing 90% of Muga silk in the country [1].

The state wise distribution of raw silk production as per the latest available statistics in the Central Silk Board 38th annual report 2020-21 is depicted in the following graph (Figure 3) [3].

Figure 3: State wise raw silk production

Figure 4 below depicts the volume of raw silk produced in India in metric tonnes and demonstrates the gradual increase in production [5].

Figure 4 : Raw Silk Production in India

3.2 Indian Silk Exports and Imports

The silk exports from India are under the categories of raw silk, silk yarn, silk fabric, silk made-ups (including furnishing materials like curtains, bedspreads, cushion covers, shawls, scarves, carpets, etc.), readymade silk garments, silk waste, silk carpets and silk handloom

products. The market share of silk exports from India in the global silk industry is estimated at around 3-3.5%, as reported by The Indian Silk Export Promotion Council (as per the latest available data as of 2020); this figure is not too significant considering India is the second-largest producer of raw silk. This may be attributed to India itself being a large domestic market for silk goods, and about 85% of silk goods produced are sold in the domestic market. However, India exports approximately 15% of its output of all types of silk goods (including value-added items). [6].

The export of silk and silk products from India are depicted Figure 5. The figure depicts an declining trend in the exports of silk [7].

As per the latest available data of 2020-21, top 10 importing countries and the value of their imports from India have been tabulated in Table 1 [8].

Table 1 : Top 10 countries importing silk from India

Sr. No.	Country	Value (in million USD)
1.	USA	76.87
2.	UAE	26.56
3.	China	20.18
4.	UK	10.92
5.	Australia	10.25
6.	Germany	8.92
7.	France	7.86
8.	Italy	6.38
9.	Spain	4.75
10.	Malaysia	4.37

Reports suggest that readymade silk garments are the largest segment generating around 35% of silk export earnings in 2020-21. Handloom silk products also contributed a substantial 27.7 %, and natural silk yarn, fabrics, and made-ups comprised 21 % of silk export earnings. Silk waste silk carpet comprised 7.6 per cent and 8.8 per cent, respectively.

Figure 5 : Export of Silk and Silk goods [9]

A significant value of silk is also imported by India, majorly from China, though this figure has been on the decline in the recent past. The import data is depicted in Figure 6 [9]

Figure 6 : Import of Silk and Silk Goods [6]

3.3 Consumer Perception and Concerns towards Silk Products

Phase two was conducted to understand the experiences and perceptions of Indian women consumers regarding the usage, care and maintenance of silk products. A survey was conducted on 200 women in the urban NCR region to understand consumer behaviour concerning silk textiles. This survey was carried out to determine the current prevalence of silk-made articles in an urban Indian household and identify the areas of concern for the care and maintenance of silk. This survey was conducted via a questionnaire comprising open-ended and closed-ended questions administered remotely via an online platform. The obtained responses were tabulated and analysed and have been graphically presented. The respondents were in the age bracket of 20-60 years. For analysis, the respondents were categorised into the following age brackets; 20-40 years and 41-60 years. The salient findings for the analysis of the responses were as follows: 54% of the respondents were from the age group of 20-40 years, while 46% belonged to the 41-60 years category.

As per Figure 7, out of the total respondents, most consumers used silk for women's apparel such as sarees, blouses, kurtas and dupattas. 92% of respondents in the age bracket of 41-60 years use silk sarees, and a lower but significant number (75%) of women in the 20-40 years bracket also used silk sarees. The use of silk in the Indian traditional garment, i.e. a saree, has been a major contributor to the success of the silk industry in India. Along with the saree, the saree blouse is also seen to be widely used by consumers. Like the saree, its use in the older age category is more prominent. 57% of women of the younger age group were seen to be using silk blouses, whereas this figure is 79% for the women in the age bracket of 41-60 years. Women's kurtas in silk are almost as popular as the saree. 82% (20-40 years) - 90% (41-60 years) of respondents wear kurtas made with silk. The use of silk dupattas is also seen to be very prevalent in both age groups. Women's lower garments like the salwar and churidar are not as popular as the upper garments like the kurta or the saree and the blouse. Their use is seen to be low in both age categories. Only around 35% of women in the 20-40 years bracket and 49% in the 41-60 years reported using churidars or salwars made of silk. Women respondents were also

asked about the purchase and use of silk kurta-pyjama by male members of their families. A larger section (43%) of women in the older age group and 26% of the younger age bracket reported the use of silk men's kurta-pyjama. This is seen as a considerable section of men consumers who are contributing to the consumption of silk. Home furnishing is also seen as a promising sector for the consumption of silk. A sizeable section of women consumers, 46% in the 41-60 age group and 36% in the age group of 20-40 years, are seen to be using home furnishings made with silk. The responses suggest that silk is still integral to the Indian wardrobe. Its use is more prominent in traditional clothing such as saree, kurtas, dupattas etc., and its use in non-traditional dress such as women's tops, shirts and trousers is also prevalent. Home furnishings are also seen as a relevant and upcoming category of silk textiles.

Figure 7 : Percentage of Women Respondents in Different Age Groups Using Various Categories of Silk Articles

It was established that silk finds a place in the modern Indian wardrobe, but the extent of its use by consumers is of concern as that determines the industry size. It was considered relevant to find out whether silk was a fabric for everyday use or only reserved for occasional use. As depicted in Figure 8, as many as 70% of consumers in the age bracket of 41-60 years and 74% in the 20-40 years bracket did not use silk for everyday apparel and home textiles and reserved it for only occasional or festive wear. It may also be noted that consumers of both age groups were almost equally disinclined to use silk as everyday articles

Figure 8 : Percentage of Women Respondents in Different Age Groups Using Silk for Everyday Use or Occasional Wear

The responses to the reasons consumers did not use silk for everyday and casual use are depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9 : Percentage of Women Respondents in Different Age Groups Citing Various Factors as Deterrents to Everyday Use of Silk

The most highlighted reason cited for limited preference for silk in everyday use was that maintenance of silk was inconvenient, followed by the seasonal usability of silk. 45% of respondents in the age category of 41-60 years and 32% of the 21-40 mentioned the cost of maintenance as the deterrent to using silk articles more frequently. The inconvenience, coupled with the cost of maintenance, are seen to be major limitations in the use of silk textiles. This, along with the fact that silk is considered seasonal wear, greatly impacts the extent of the use of silk by consumers. Though it is considerably more expensive than the other common-use fibres, only 20% (41-60 years) and 26% (20-40 years) of respondents reported that as the reason for limited usage. The response to this question revealed that the primary reason for the lesser adoption of silk textiles is the inconvenience and recurring cost of their care and maintenance. If the care and maintenance of silk fabrics could be made more convenient for consumers in these terms, their usage may probably be enhanced.

The respondents were also asked about the preferred practices of cleaning and maintenance of silk articles. Figure 10 graphically represents the responses obtained.

Figure 10 : Percentage of Women Respondents in Different Age Groups Preferring Various Laundry Practices for Silk

The responses to this question strongly indicated that a very large section of consumers in both age categories preferred to dry clean silk. The age of the respondents did not affect the preferred choice of laundering silk textiles. Responses indicate that a large segment of the respondents (85%) preferred professional dry-cleaning of silk items. In contrast, very few adopted hand washing, and only 2 women in each age category machine-washed their silk articles. This trend probably is the reason consumers find care and maintenance inconvenient and thus limit its use to occasional wear. The need to dry-clean is a significant deterrent in the popularity of silk as it escalates maintenance costs, damages the ecosystem, and adds to inconvenience.

A need was felt to identify why consumers favour dry-cleaning silk instead of home laundering. The respondents who attempted home laundering of silks were inquired about their problems faced when silks are washed at. The responses have been depicted graphically in Figure 11.

Figure 11 : Percentage of Women Respondents in Different Age Groups Facing Various Concerns in Home Laundering of Silk

Results indicated (Figure 11) brings out that more percentage of respondents in the older age group (41-60) have cited problems in the home laundering of silk. This may be because the women in this age group either use more silk textiles or undertake more hand washing of silk and thus are more aware of the challenges faced. Respondents indicated that colour bleeding, shrinkage, difficulty in stain removal, and the inability to get a perfectly ironed finish were the primary reasons consumers preferred dry-cleaning over home laundering. Shrinkage was reported by 98% of the women in the older age group, whereas only 56% of respondents in the age category of 20-40 years reported problems of shrinkage. Though shrinkage is not a common phenomenon in silk, consumers may have experienced this with silk blend fabrics. A large portion of the women (65%) in the 41-60 years category also reported the problem of colour bleeding, whereas only 24% of the younger age group identified this as a problem with the home washing of silk. It is felt that this discrepancy may be because not many users in the young age category undertake home laundering of silk or use fewer silk articles. Most women expressed dissatisfaction regarding the inability to get a smooth finish by ironing at home after washing. Once again, the percentage

of women reporting this was higher in the 41-60 years group (63%) as compared to the 20-40 years group (48%). A relatively lesser percentage of women also pointed out the difficulty in stain removal from silk articles.

Those respondents who only sent out silk articles for dry-cleaning were asked for reasons for inhibition in the home laundering of silk. The responses have been presented in Figure 12. The responses indicate that the most cited reasons consumers prefer dry-cleaning. Here again, a much larger percentage of respondents from the 41-60 years category have identified the shortcomings that demand the dry cleaning of silks. The reason most highlighted here is the fear of colour loss from the silk textile and the staining of adjacent areas. The largest percentage of respondents, i.e., 65% (41-60 years) and 44% (20-40 years), identified colour bleeding as the problem that requires them to get dry cleaning of silk instead of home laundering. A significant number of respondents also felt silk garments or other products lose their shine and lustre if washed at home. This concern was also related to the colour or dye quality of silk fabrics. Many respondents in the 41-60 and 20-40 year age categories (46% and 37%, respectively) had the perception that silk is weak and thus unsuitable for home laundering. This is a myth, as silk fibre is known for its good tensile strength. A common reason, also cited by a large number of respondents, is the tendency to shrink, either of the fabric shell or of the cotton lining usually used in silk made-ups.

Figure 12: Percentage of Women Respondents in Different Age Groups Citing Various Reasons for Choosing Dry Cleaning of Silk Articles

4. Conclusion

India has been producing silk since the Pre-Vedic era. The Indian subcontinent is well known for its prominent position in the world silk map. The Indian silk industry comprises of silk production including sericulture, yarn production, fabric manufacturing, finishing as well as product development. The silk industry spans across the country and is also a major contributor to the rural economy. Traditional and contemporary methods of production coexist to produce a wide variety of silk fabrics with distinct uses throughout the world. India significantly exports several silk products and at the same time also has a large domestic consumption of silk, particularly owing to our traditional clothing practices. The domestic consumption of silk is primarily comprised of

sarees, blouses, kurtas, dupattas, and other clothing items. Recent times have seen the expansion of the use of silk in the home textiles sector too. The present study focuses on identifying the current status of the industry and understanding consumer concerns about the use of silk products. The findings can be of use in strengthening the position of the silk industry in India. Results indicated that one crucial factor that seems to influence the diminishing use of silk is the consumers' experience that silk requires expensive care and maintenance. Most consumers resort to professional dry-cleaning of silk, which is not only inconvenient and costly but is also essentially

environmentally toxic. One of the main reasons for not being able to launder silk at home was reported to be its tendency to bleed colour and loose sheen. Interestingly, people perceive shrinkage as a problem in silk home laundering. This could actually be due to the shrinkage of cotton lining in most of the silk garments, which is very common and leads to puckers and overall change in the size and fit of the garment. The findings are crucial in identifying the lacunae in the silk dyeing industry, which need to be addressed by proposing dyes and processes for silk colouration that would offer enhanced consumer satisfaction.

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